

Application of Collaborative Editing to Software-Engineering Projects

*Uwe M. Borghoff and Gunnar Teege**

Institut für Informatik, Technische Universität München
Postfach 20 24 20, D-8000 München 2, Germany

Abstract

Collaborative editing is a major research topic within synchronous CSCW-applications. While preserving some kind of consistency and transparency, it allows different users at different locations to edit a shared document at the same time. In the past a variety of different approaches have been designed with different functionality ranging from pure shared outline editors to fully distributed document preparation systems.

Software-engineering projects are an ideal playground because they typically consist of a variety of different small subproject documents. The impact of collaborative editors to SE projects is discussed. Furthermore, we develop design concepts that should be essential for user-friendly collaborative editing and collaboration-aware group interaction. A collaborative editor, called IRIS, has been prototypically implemented to improve SE project handling. It supports distributed editing with replicated data and provides dynamic voting for consistency as well as sophisticated notification mechanisms in the context of well-structured documents.

1 Introduction

Typically users of a computer system are isolated. The key concept in distributed computing is transparency. Where collaboration-aware group interaction is needed, groupware is a way out of isolation. Collaborative editing is a major research topic within synchronous CSCW-applications. Besides all problems concerning data integrity, consistency, and replication control, collaborative editors have to deal with

- sophisticated notification mechanisms
- management of structural information
- versioning and management of history information

*Email: {borghoff,teege}@informatik.tu-muenchen.de

Collaborative editors support the creation and manipulation of project plans that are based on documents. SE projects are an ideal playground because they typically consist of a variety of different small subproject documents. Among many others, data models, function lists, or specification lists must be managed. Therefore, the impact of collaborative editors on SE projects is an interesting research topic.

SE documents are structured to simplify the pure editing process and to clarify the SE project planning. This interrelation between pure editing and project planning should be studied. Unlike other papers that deal with dependencies within SE projects, we will discuss a possibly distributed management of replicated structural information. Structure management has been studied in the context of collaborative editors to allow different users at different locations to edit a shared document at the same time.

Organization of the Paper

Sect. 2 describes previous work in this area whereas Sect. 3 shows our new approach. We develop design concepts that should be essential for user-friendly collaborative editing and collaboration-aware group interaction. Sect. 4 briefly describes our new collaborative editor IRIS. It supports distributed editing with replicated data and provides dynamic voting for consistency as well as sophisticated notification mechanisms. Sect. 5 concludes this paper and gives ideas for further research.

2 Previous Work

The Collaborative Editing System (CES) [9] is one of the first shared editors that distinguishes between textual and structural information. A text is partitioned into sections that are owned by each author. Like CES, Quilt [7] uses sections as editable granularity.

On the other hand, editors like the Group Outline Viewing Editor (GROVE) [6] or toolkits like DistEdit [15] provide no structural information. GROVE is fine-grained and supports real-time updates on character-level using insert and delete primitives. A transformation algorithm based on priorities and semantics of the operations permits highly concurrent access. Floor passing in DistEdit allows a single user, the so-called master, to take a turn at editing the file. All other users, the so-called observers, are able to watch the master's edit in real-time.

MMM [1] supports simultaneous real-time collaboration with fine-grained sharing. This includes simultaneous access to the same text string or graphical object [2]. MACE [22] supports variable editable granularity, i.e., a user acquires a pair of locks for the text fragment in question. Together, the top and bottom locks mark an area of text that can be updated without interference from others as soon as the locks are held by a centralized editor-server. Other lock-based approaches to concurrent editing are MULE [25] and MultimETH [19]. MULE's editable granularity is a line or a block of plain text, whereas MultimETH collaboratively creates, edits and manages multimedia documents consisting of a number of structural elements, e.g., title, headings, chapters, sections, and whatsoever. The structural elements have a hierarchical relationship and a particular content, e.g., text, graphic, or bitmap.

There are a variety of other approaches for collaborative editing such as, CoAuthor [10], Collaborative Annotator [17], ForComment [24], GroupSystems [23], MMConf [5], PREP [21], and Shared Books [18].

Gibbs [8] summarizes a number of CSCW-applications and illustrates how they may be used at various stages within the software development process. Among others, multiuser editors and co-authoring systems are described. In [26], Schlichter and Borghoff state that it is crucial for a multiuser editor to support replicated documents, and to integrate notification mechanisms into the concurrency control algorithms in order to notify group members of changes and activities in the context of a common document. Mercury [14], for instance, has knowledge of import and export dependencies of software modules and provides an inter-module notification mechanism. An interesting approach to offer notification of history information to guide work is presented by Hill *et al.* In [11], the terms *edit wear* and *read wear* are defined. Edit wear portrays the document's authorship history, while read wear portrays the document's readership history.

3 Collaborative Editing and SE projects

Here, we first present a model for collaborative editing that mediates coordination and cooperation. Then we show how to apply this model to software-engineering projects. Finally, we describe the features automatically obtained for an SE system from this model as well as typical SE system features which are not included.

3.1 Collaborative Editing

In our model of collaborative editing we consider the maintenance and usage of a (logical) document structure to be a central point. In contrast to a single user editor, the existence of other users editing the same document at the same time creates a need for a common logical view of the document structure. This document structure allows the specification of logical units and logical positions within the document which are the main base for giving the user all kinds of information that is related to the question "where am I working and what are the others doing?".

The existence of such a logical structure naturally suggests a set of operations which use and update the structure. The collaborative editor should be able to manipulate the structural information, to hold versions of structural changes, and, most importantly, to manage an update-history. Notification and display mechanisms for structural changes along the version/history tree should be provided.

In order to create a system that can be used effectively, we emphasize electronic document standards, such as the Office Document Architecture (ODA) [12] or the Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML) [13]. ODA defines schemes to describe data structures as well as rules for the document layout using standardized semantics. Furthermore, a syntax for the interchange of this information is given. SGML, on the other hand, contains a syntax to exchange document structures without providing an explicit definition of the semantics of such structures. Therefore, SGML-based systems need additional agreements between the corresponding sites.

Later on we will describe which features are of interest and what functionality is irrelevant for us. But no matter what electronic document standard is used, the functionalities of the editor can be separated into modules based upon the kind of information used and its method of usage.

Fig. 1 shows the resulting modularized editor with an

Fig. 1. Structure of a Collaborative Editor.

operation layer (editing, coordinating, profiling, etc.) on top of a data layer (content, structure, history, static user information).

Data Layer

Content Information: This is the actual content of the document. It corresponds to the document in a single user editor. In this paper and the following model, we only consider textual information. In a multimedia document, however, the textual information could also contain pictures and sounds. Note, that commands for layout specification like tabulators or complex structuring commands for a text processing system also belong to the textual information.

Structural Information: The structural information is an “explicit” document structure. It is seen and manipulated by the users. It is used by the editor mainly to give the users a compact view of the actions of users in the document. Both the structural information and the textual information also have

an “implicit structure” only seen by the editor. It is used by the editor in the usual way to coordinate updates of this information.

For the implicit structure, a sequence of individually lockable records is sufficient. The explicit structure should be multi-level (like a document structure with chapters, sections, subsections, paragraphs, appendices, headings, footnotes, figures and tables) to allow *logical* views of different grain in different parts of the document and to associate content with structural elements. To be more precise, we do not cope with a *layout* view that associates content with structural elements relating to presentation media, such as pages or areas within a particular page. Instead, we only need the structure to describe the document as seen by the user when it is edited.

The explicit structure can be used in three principal ways. First, to inform the user about actions performed on the document, second, to coordinate the actions performed on the document on a higher

level, and finally, to support actions of a single user, like positioning in the document. In all three cases the structure is used to identify parts of or positions in the document.

History Information: The history information holds previous versions of the document. Furthermore, it stores the activities of users who have already left the editing session. It enables active users to identify past modifications and to recognize “historic” work on the document at all.

Static User Information: The static user information can be stored in a common database. The entries cover phone numbers, Email addresses, or even bitmap photographs of the individual users of the system. All information can be displayed in a special window to allow for direct user interaction (voice, messages, etc.) or simply for “nicer” cooperation (photograph). The latter approach has been successfully implemented in GROVE. Predefined messages, such as “please free your locked section”, can be sent to the user who has locked a section.

Operation Layer

Basic Editing: This module contains all the functionality which only uses and changes the textual information. Thus, it is equivalent to the functionality of a single user editor.

Structure Editing: The document structure normally evolves during the existence of the document. Thus, analogous to the basic editing of the contents, the editor must allow editing of the document structure. This functionality is separated from basic editing because the editing operations for the document structure differ from those for the contents. Typical operations are:

- defining a new part
- removing an existing part
- moving a part to another position in the structure

Implicit Coordination: Both the basic editing module and the structure editing module must coordinate concurrent updates. This is a typical implicit coordination that is done by the editor itself.

Explicit Coordination: Besides an implicit way of hidden coordination, explicit coordination operations should be provided at the user level. This

module contains all functionality for explicit coordination. Typical cases are the explicit locking of a document part by a user, a request to unlock a part, or even requesting another user to work on a part.

The locks in this module may either be “soft”, i.e., they are only shown to the other users, or “hard”, i.e., the editor guarantees the exclusive access to a locked part.

Dynamic Profile: This module contains all functions that give one user information about the actions of the other users, e.g., joining the editing session, changing a certain document part or locking a document part.

The module uses the document structure as a basis to show which document parts are involved. The dynamic profile is also involved in displaying “historic” changes.

Other Features: The document structure can be used for other purposes as well, which need not have coordination aspects.

Examples are positioning on the beginning/end of a document part or defining the content of a part to be a region to which a basic editing function like “delete” should be applied.

3.2 Application to Software-Engineering

The model presented in the last section was originally designed for true collaborative editing of text documents, such as books or articles. For the remainder of this section, we will show that the model can easily be adapted to more powerful tasks. In fact it is useful for all tasks which involve several people working on items which can be stored and manipulated by a computer.

Software-engineering is an especially well-fitting and interesting example. All phases of the SE cycle can be described as writing or changing texts. In the coding phase the text is the program source. In the other phases it consists of documents like requirement analyses or error reports. The existence of an explicit document structure which is separated from the contents in our model allows the combination of all these documents into a single structured document. Hence most of the activities in an SE project are simply the collaborative editing of this document.

In this way all mechanisms from the collaborative editor automatically apply to software-engineering and they are as important here as they are for editing simple text documents. The mechanisms are as follows:

- coordination of concurrent work (explicit and implicit). The implicit coordination module supports the concurrent editing of the overall structure and on single files like a program source. The explicit coordination module supports locking of files, file groups, or file parts. It also provides communication mechanisms between the current participants to coordinate their work.
- version control and change of history. Version control is compatible with the document structure. Thus the editor can do version management on all levels like single procedures in source files, single files, multi-file documents, or whole project phases. The history mechanism provides all project members with a structured project history which can tell the times when documents were changed and who did the change.
- information about the current activities. This part of the dynamic profile module gives an overview of the current project activities. It can help to give the participants a feeling of what happens in their “neighborhood”. This is the basis for short-term coordination.
- maintenance and retrieval of all documents associated with the project. All documents are part of the structured project document. Thus the editing and positioning functions of the editor, directly support the organization of all these documents.

As a digression, it is interesting to note that we are well aware of the problems arising when every project member has full access to the information about the activities of all members. This becomes more severe for large projects with a hierarchically structured team. In these cases the dynamic profile module should be enhanced by an ask-and-grant mechanism or other mechanisms to restrict the access to user specific information.

All mechanisms from the collaborative editor are useful for SE projects, however there are some typical requirements for SE project maintenance that are not part of the model. Besides the rather simple requirement that the document must not be restricted to the content of a single file, the most important points are:

- dependencies between parts of the document
- planning and scheduling of activities

However, these are also useful for editing simple text documents. Thus we plan to use them as a basis to enhance the collaborative editing model to a general model for organizing collaborative work on computer representable information.

Summarizing this section, we have shown a way to combine collaborative editing and software-engineering in a way that is fruitful for both sides. Concepts from either domain can be transferred and applied to the other one.

4 The IRIS approach

Here we propose our new distributed multiuser editor IRIS.¹ It uses a certain explicit structure that is flexible enough to be adapted to a wide variety of document contents. In the following we first describe the IRIS features concerning basic collaborative editing, and then we present the handling and usage of the explicit structure.

4.1 Basic Features of IRIS

Unlike other approaches, IRIS uses a distributed replication control scheme based on dynamic voting (see Tab. 1) for the textual as well as for the structural information. Dynamic voting schemes are well known in the context of distributed file systems [3]. As far as the authors know, the application to a CSCW-system supporting SE projects is a novel approach.

Currently² IRIS provides the following features:

- Manipulation of alphanumeric documents stored in ASCII-format. Graphics or multimedia elements are not supported so far.

Documents are structured (cf. Sect. 4.2). The description of the document structure is stored independently from the content. Like CES and MultiMETH, IRIS allows for structural changes without harm to the textual information.

The document content may consist of several parts which are stored in separate files. The files may be distributed among several hosts. The document structure supplies the necessary location information to the editor for accessing all parts.

- The document parts used during an editing session are locally stored, i.e., a new user is dynamically provided with the entire document part in question as soon as he/she joins the session. If all users work on the same part, it is fully-replicated.

¹In Greek mythology, IRIS is a female messenger of the gods that reliably delivers messages from Zeus to human beings, and vice versa. This role of mediator together with high reliability is also demanded on our collaborative editor.

²Based on two master's theses by Koch [16] and Mäkiö [20] as well as developments of the authors.

	data storage	replication	concurrency control
CES	distributed	partly, i.e., structural information fully replicated, text units not replicated	transactions (peculiarity: tickle-locks)
DistEdit	distributed	fully replicated	write-all-read-any or floor-passing
GROVE	distributed	fully replicated	transformations based on priorities and semantics of operations
IRIS	distributed	fully replicated	dynamic voting
MACE	centralized	none (local caching of text units currently processed)	centralized editor-server (write locks)
MMM	centralized	none	simple locks
MULE	distributed	fully replicated	centralized lock-server
MultimETH	centralized	none	simple locks
PREP	centralized	none	transactions
Quilt	centralized	none	transactions
Shared Books	centralized	none (caching of particular text units on request)	simple locks

Tab. 1. Data Storage and Replication Control Schemes.

Obviously, the degree of replication of a particular document part may change dynamically. It equals the number of active users editing this part.

- IRIS guarantees the consistency of the replicated units even in the presence of site or link failures. Note that network partitionings do not harm the consistency of the entire document.
- In order to increase scrolling performance, read accesses are granted to all parts of the document at any time.

Users are notified, however, if parts of the read document are locked or possibly obsolete. This display/notification mechanism of locked areas helps to avoid concurrent write accesses in advance without an explicit prepare-to-write request.

- Write accesses, on the other hand, are synchronized using explicit as well as implicit locks. These locks are set within the multi-phase commit protocol of the dynamic voting approach. Performance reasons constrain the editable granularity. Fine-grained updates are not possible and seem, in the context of SE project plans, not to be necessary. Unlike GROVE, typical brainstorm activities are not supported.

The document structure suggests an update unit with variable editable granularity. Users are informed about changes as soon as the update is completed and has been mutually accepted by a logical majority. Due to the chosen voting approach, locks and version numbers are set or incremented, respec-

tively, on the update units. Read and write accesses are based on the update units as well.

4.2 Explicit Structure

In IRIS, we chose the logical structure to have the form of the *specific logical structure* from the Open Document Architecture [12]. Here we briefly describe the relevant parts of this structure.

The ODA specific logical structure is a tree of objects that are typed in four ways:

- document logical root, the root of the tree
- content portion, a contiguous part of the document content
- basic logical object, a node with only content portions as subnodes
- composite logical object, inner node with no content portions as subnodes

Every object has a number. The sequence of numbers on the path from the document logical root to an object must identify the object uniquely and is called its *object identifier*. Every object which is not a content portion may have a *user visible name*, which is an arbitrary string like “function model” or “Chapter 1” as shown in Fig. 2.

Names are usually defined or changed by the users, but they may also be generated automatically. For the subnodes of every node a sequential order is defined which

Fig. 2. Part of the Explicit Structure of the IRIS Project.

may be different from the order of their identifying numbers. Note that this induces a sequential order on the set of all content portions, and, most importantly, makes a content portion an ideal candidate as an update unit.

The content portions together are the document content, which in IRIS is stored separately from the structure. At present, every content portion belongs to exactly one basic logical object. For the longer term, different basic logical objects may be linked to a particular content portion to avoid storing redundant information and to allow for simple cross-referencing. Anyway, the content portions were chosen to be the update units for accesses by the editor. In a text document they usually correspond to a single paragraph.

The explicit structure itself consists of the tree without the content portions. This type of structure allows for the necessary flexibility. A tree node can describe a paragraph, a chapter, a declaration in a program source, a whole document or even a set of documents. Thus, it supports the application to software-engineering projects as described in Sect. 3.2.

In IRIS, basic editing is done in one or more usual text windows which show a part of or all of the content portions concatenated in their sequential order. The explicit structure is presented to the user in the form of one or more *structure views*. A structure view depicts one object from the structure in an iconic way. The concrete appearance is a rectangular space on the screen. As content it may display one or more of the following items that are individually and interactively configurable by

the user:

- the identifying number
- the user visible name
- the sequence of iconic representations of all subordinate objects in their sequential order provided it is no basic logical object

Fig. 3 depicts two possible structure views of the node named “design phase” from the structure in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Two Structure Views of the Node “design phase”.

A structure view either shows the current situation, or it may show the structure of an already obsolete version together with the corresponding possibly obsolete content version. In the context of software-engineering projects (cf. Sect. 3.2) a structure view illustrates a part of or all of the project documents or document parts. It can be used by itself to navigate through the set of project documents.

Besides basic editing, the editor modules described in Sect. 3.1 use structure views in a common way as their input or output medium. Supported input types include the following:

- selecting one or more objects by their iconic representation
- selecting a position between objects, or at the beginning or end of an object
- selecting a user visible name, or identifying the number of an object

Supported output types include the following:

- marking an iconic object representation (shading or coloring) or a part of it
- pointing to an iconic object representation (e.g., with an arrow) from outside of the structure view

Structure editing uses all three input types. It allows the user to select objects for deletion, to select positions for creating new objects or moving existing objects, and to select names or numbers for changes.

Explicit coordination uses object selection for specifying parts to be locked or for referencing parts in messages to other users. It uses marking of objects to show locked parts, and it uses pointing or marking to show parts referenced in a message. Dynamic profiling uses both output types to show where current or former activities took place in the document. The other features use selection of objects and positions to define regions and positions in the content window, and both output types to show positions or objects which are related to certain basic editing operations initiated by the user.

5 Conclusion

This paper provided basic design concepts for collaborative editing that are essential for user-friendly and collaboration-aware group interaction in the context of SE projects based on documents. As an example, we proposed our approach, IRIS, which supports distributed editing with replicated data and provides dynamic voting for consistency as well as sophisticated notification mechanisms. IRIS is implemented in C and

runs on our HP-workstation cluster. The ISIS toolkit is used to provide the multicast feature. The graphical interface has been written using the InterViews 3.01 software package.

What is missing so far is a detailed discussion of structure management, i.e., which operations on the structure should be defined. Should the editor know about structure dependencies, and should the editor itself detect modifications that require notification? Furthermore, we plan to combine asynchronous and synchronous collaborative systems. As an example, we will show this combination for Teege's newly developed activity support system TACTS [27] and an extended version of our proposed collaborative editor. For more details about IRIS and some answers to the questionnaire, the reader is referred to [4, 28].

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